

**DEBT MANAGEMENT OFFICE
NIGERIA**

**DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL
TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020
AMOUNT IN NAIRA**

SN	STATE	DEBT STOCK (N)
1	ABIA	92,806,570,546.03
2	ADAMAWA	100,599,569,235.97
3	AKWA IBOM	239,209,746,919.94
4	ANAMBRA	59,013,845,976.50
5	BAUCHI	97,933,063,584.67
6	BAYELSA	150,057,580,348.08
7	BENUE	128,504,831,985.51
8	BORNO	90,369,619,974.97
9	CROSS-RIVER	165,019,082,432.50
10	DELTA	235,860,479,518.82
11	EBONYI	41,273,963,348.58
12	EDO	82,916,811,325.65
13	EKITI	77,072,844,596.55
14	ENUGU	62,436,497,337.43
15	GOMBE	90,503,282,526.59
16	IMO	158,174,623,598.44
17	JIGAWA	36,039,966,666.27
18	KADUNA	72,503,331,825.58
19	KANO	116,999,956,070.87
20	KATSINA	44,416,331,545.82
21	KEBBI	67,315,419,254.61
22	KOGI	73,314,904,696.35
23	KWARA	63,366,236,320.99
24	LAGOS	493,318,231,673.72
25	NASARAWA	61,299,995,407.54
26	NIGER	65,601,207,473.58
27	OGUN	148,772,734,071.17
28	ONDO	63,677,729,196.02
29	OSUN	136,125,242,955.06
30	OYO	99,943,412,785.14
31	PLATEAU	127,012,622,276.11
32	RIVERS*	266,936,225,793.65
33	SOKOTO	48,089,793,082.99
34	TARABA	122,746,246,998.60
35	YOBE	29,230,547,154.25
36	ZAMFARA	79,286,884,618.37
37	FCT	101,949,645,786.10
Total		4,189,699,078,909.01

Important Notes

1 Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.

2* Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018